

ASSESSMENT OF IMPROVED YAM PRODUCTION TECHNOLOGIES UTILIZED AND IT'S EFFECT ON THE YAM OUTPUT AMONG YAM FARMERS IN BENUE AND NIGER STATES, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the utilization of improved yam production technologies and its effects on yam output among farmers in Benue and Niger states, Nigeria. A three-stage sampling technique was employed to select 399 respondents, with 200 from Niger State and 199 from Benue State. Primary data were collected through structured questionnaires, and the analysis involved descriptive statistics (mean, percentages, and frequency count) and inferential statistics, particularly multiple regression. The results indicated that the mean age of respondents in Niger State was 43 years, whereas in Benue State, it was 40 years. Additionally, 94.0% and 82.0% of respondents in Niger and Benue States, respectively, were married, and 95.0% and 77.5% were males. The mean household size was 8 persons in Niger State and 9 persons in Benue State. Regarding education, 71.0% and 69.4% of respondents in Benue and Niger States had formal education, respectively. Furthermore, the study revealed that 93.0% and 79.0% of respondents in Niger and Benue States, respectively, utilized improved yam technologies. Multiple regression analysis estimates on the effects of improved yam production technologies on yam output revealed that the coefficient of mulching (0.4371), use of herbicides (4159.544), fertilizer (47.230) and land preparation (192.669) in Niger State, while use of improved planting method (0.8531), use of herbicide (1.3466), fertilizer application (0.1259) in Benue State were positive and had significant effects on yam output at 1%, 5% and 10% level of probability. Meanwhile, the coefficient of staking (-0.2381) in Benue State was negative and had significant effects on yam output. It is therefore recommended that various agencies saddled with the responsibilities of developing improved yam production technologies should make it available and affordable for enhanced utilization by the farmers.

Keyword: Yam, technologies, output, effects, production, Benue

INTRODUCTION

Up to 40% of all calories consumed in Africa come from the yam (*Dioscorea*), making it a major source of carbohydrates (FAO, 2010). Because of its high yield and productivity, it plays an important role in tropical climates. Yams are becoming more and more popular throughout the world as a cheap source of energy feed for ruminants and other livestock. Its cultivation and use have a long history; in South-Eastern Nigeria, annual harvest

festivals are held in honour of it, and marriage contracts hold cultural significance for different communities.

Yam tubers can be cooked, roasted, fried, or crushed in a variety of culinary uses. In addition, they can be dried, chopped, and processed to make "Amala" yam flour (Usongo et al., 2014). Beyond its culinary applications, yam is known for its therapeutic qualities, which include the treatment of hypercholesterolemia and diabetes mellitus

(Okigbo and Ogbonna, 2006). But yam has problems too, like poor yield, spoilage during storage, and trouble keeping for long periods. These limitations are exacerbated by high production expenses, which include costly seed yams, manpower, staking materials, agrochemicals, and soil preparation (Ogaraku and Usman, 2008).

To solve these issues, improved yam production technologies have been developed. These include yam miniset, sophisticated staking techniques, optimum soil preparation, high-yielding cultivars, mulching, pest and disease resistance, suggested fertilizer administration, and weed management. The aim of the study is to evaluate how farmers in Benue and Niger states are using these improved yam production technology and how that has affected yam output.

The specific objectives are to:

- i. describe the socio-economic characteristics of the yam farmers in the study area;
- ii. examine the improved yam production technologies utilized by farmers in the study area,
- iii. Access the effects of improved yam production technologies on yam output of the respondent.

METHODOLOGY

The review was directed in the Benue and Niger Provinces of Nigeria.

Nigeria's North Central Geopolitical Zone includes Benue State. possessing an abundance of land, estimated at 5.09 million hectares. This covers 5.4% of the land that is owned by the public. The State's estimated amount of arable land is 3.8 million hectares, according to the Benue Geographic Data Framework (BENGIS, 2018). Five distinct states share boundaries with the state: Nasarawa to the north, Taraba to the east, Cross Waterway to the southeast, Enugu to the southwest, and Kogi to the west. According to BENGIS (2018), the state is divided into three horticultural zones: the Eastern, Northern, and Focal zones. These zones comprise 23 Local

Government Areas, with Makurdi serving as the headquarters.

With 4,219,244 residents and 413,159 homestead families, the population of the state was estimated by the NPC in 2006 to be 5,536,070 by the end of 2018 using a 3.8% growth rate. The majority of these ranch families are rural residents. Natives of Benue State primarily control agriculture. Benue State, often referred to as the "Food Basket of the Nation," earns this title due to its rich agricultural resources. The state is prolific in the production of groundnuts, rice, yams, cassava, maize, and various other cash and food crops. It boasts an abundance of ingredients such as yams, millet, sorghum, sesame, and a diverse array of foods including citrus, mango, and soybeans.

Niger State, situated in the Northern Central geopolitical zone of Nigeria, was carved out from the former North-Western State. Bordered by Zamfara to the North, Kebbi to the Northwest, Kogi to the South, Kwara to the Southwest, and flanked by Kaduna State and the Federal Capital Territory to the Northeast and Southeast respectively, Niger State is administratively divided into three Agricultural Zones—namely, I, II, and III Zones, each comprising 8, 9, and 8 local government areas (LGAs), respectively (Niger State Geographical Information System (NIGIS), 2018). With a total land area of 74,244 sq. km, constituting about 8% of Nigeria's overall landmass, Niger State stands as the largest in the country. The 2006 national population census recorded a total population of 3,950,249 for Niger State (National Population Commission, Niger State, 2006). However, the projected population by the end of 2018, based on a 3.4% growth rate, reached 5,518,612. Covering approximately 86,000 km² (or around 8.6 million hectares), Niger State represents about 9.3% of Nigeria's total land area (Niger State Geographical Information System (NIGIS), 2018).

Agriculture serves as the backbone of Niger

State's economy, with over 80% of the population depending either directly or indirectly on it for their livelihoods. Due to its favourable location, climate, and soil conditions, the state stands as one of the largest and most fertile agricultural lands in the country, capable of producing a substantial portion of Nigeria's staple crops. The people of Niger State cultivate a variety of crops, including yams, maize, rice, soybeans, cassava, okra, tomatoes, pepper, melon, shea butter, and various leafy vegetables. Additionally, Niger State provides ample opportunities for grazing, fishing, and forestry.

The study used a three-stage sample technique and focused on yam producers in the Nigerian states of Niger and Benue. Six Local Government Areas (LGAs) were chosen in the initial round because of their predominance in yam production. One LGA was purposefully chosen from each agricultural zone in the selected states. In the second phase, villages in the states of Benue and Niger were chosen proportionately (10%). There were 399 participants in the study's total sample.

Primary data for the study were collected through structured questionnaires and interview schedules. Interviews were conducted for respondents who couldn't read or write, while questionnaires were administered to literate yam farmers. Trained enumerators proficient in the local language facilitated the primary data collection process. Information gathered included the socio-economic characteristics of yam farmers in the study area, such as age, educational level, household size, farming experience, marital status, extension contact, and various yam production technologies used, along with their effects on yam output.

The analytical tools employed in this study included both descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistics, such as mean, percentages, and frequency counts, were utilized, while inferential statistics involved multiple regression analysis to determine the impact of advanced yam technology utilization

on farmers' yam output.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

According to the findings, respondents' average age was forty-three years old in Benue State and forty years old in Niger State. This shows that most of the responders were in their prime of productivity and were looking for new ideas to improve their methods of production. This runs counter to Ajieh's (2012) findings, which indicated that elderly farmers produced more yams. In line with Mohammed's observations (2015), the data also showed that a sizable percentage of yam farmers in the States of Niger (94.0%) and Benue (82.0%) were married, highlighting the importance of marriage for procreation and providing support for farming activities. Furthermore, the results of Nahanga and Becvarova (2014) are consistent with the observation that most respondents were male 95.0% in Niger State and 77.5% in Benue State. This could be attributed to women's household work and the production of less demanding arable crops.

According to the examination of household sizes, 60.5% of respondents in Benue State and 42.7% in Niger State, respectively, reported having 6–10 people living in their homes, with typical household sizes of 8 and 9 members. There may be benefits in terms of the availability of farm labour due to the states' comparable household sizes. Furthermore, a sizable portion of yam growers in both states—71.0% in Benue State and 96.4% in Niger State - had completed formal education, indicating a high degree of literacy among farmers.

Furthermore, the mean farming experience was 20 years in Niger State and 17 years in Benue State. This indicates that a significant proportion of respondents in the study area had considerable farming experience, likely influencing their decision-making regarding the adoption of improved technologies for enhanced production.

Table 1: Distribution of the respondents according to their socio-economic characteristics

Variables	Benue State (n=200)		Niger State (n=199)	
	Freq	Percentage	Freq	Percentage
Age (years				
< 26	14	7.0	4	2.0
26 – 35	28	14.0	46	23.1
36 – 45	68	34.0	112	56.3
46 – 55	88	44.0	32	16.1
> 55	2	1.0	5	2.5
Mean	43		40	
Marital Status				
Single	22	11.0	8	4.0
Married	164	82.0	187	94.0
Divorced	7	3.5	2	1.0
Widowed	1	0.5	2	1.0
Widower	6	3.0	0	0
Gender				
Male	155	77.5	189	95.0
Female	45	22.5	10	5.0
Household size				
< 6	40	20.0	53	26.6
6 – 10	121	60.5	85	42.7
11 – 15	27	13.5	57	28.6
> 15	12	6.0	4	2.1
Mean	8		9	
Educational status				
Primary	24	12.0	44	22.1
Secondary	42	21.0	69	34.7
Tertiary	77	38.5	25	12.6
Non formal	13	6.5	49	24.6
Adult	44	22.0	12	6.0
Farming experience				
< 11	52	26.0	27	13.6
11 – 20	94	47.0	99	49.7
21 – 30	36	18.0	54	27.1
> 30	18	9.0	19	9.6
Mean	17		20	

Field Survey, 2019

The distribution of respondents based on their farm size is presented in Table 2. In Niger State, yam farmers cultivated an average of 3.4 hectares of land, compared to 1.6 hectares in Benue State. This suggests that yam farming was more prevalent among Niger State farmers than Benue State farmers. Also, yam farmers across the states are small-scale farmers who could be producing mainly for consumption and little for sale. Additional research revealed

that 75.0% of yam growers in Benue State and 83.4% of farmers in Niger obtain their land through inheritance. An important factor in the application of advanced industrial technology is labour. The result revealed that 59% and 28.2% of yam farmers in Benue and Niger States used hired labour. This finding showed that hired and family labour was used in yam production.

Table 2: Distribution of respondents based on farm size, acquisition and labour usage

Variables	Benue State (n=200)		Niger State (n=199)	
	Freq.	%	Freq.	%
Farm size (Ha)				
< 1.1	102	51.0	37	18.6
1.1 - 3.0	83	41.5	78	39.2
> 3.0	15	7.5	84	42.2
Mean	1.62		3.44	
Farmland acquisition				
Inheritance	150	75.0	166	83.4
Lease/rent	28	14.0	25	12.6
Purchase	22	11.0	2	1.0
Others	0	0.0	6	3.0
Labour usage mostly				
Family	64	32.0	46	23.0
Hired	118	59.0	56	28.2
Communal	10	5.0	0	0.0
Family and Hired	8	4.0	97	48.8

Field Survey, 2019

According to Table 3, the majority of respondents in the states of Niger and Benue, respectively, were aware of enhanced yam technologies, with 90.5% and 80.0% knowing

this. Overall, both States have far greater levels of awareness of enhanced yam cultivation, which is anticipated to raise yam output in the research area.

Table 3: Awareness of improved yam production technologies

Variables	Benue State(n=200)	Niger State(n=199)	Pooled(n=399)
	Freq (%)	Freq (%)	Freq (%)
Awareness of improved yam production technologies			
Aware	160 (80.0)	180 (90.5)	340 (85.2)
Not aware	40 (20.0)	19 (9.5)	59 (14.8)

Sources: Field Survey, 2019

Table 4 showed that in Benue State and Niger, respectively, 79.0% and 93.0% of respondents adopted enhanced yam technology. This implies that the majority of responders produced yams using more modern techniques. This outcome is in line with the research done by Omotesho *et al.* (2012), who discovered that more Nigerian farmers in Kwara State employed improved yam-producing techniques. Additionally, 90.2% and 58.2% of respondents in the states of Niger and Benue, respectively, reported using moulds to prepare their land; this suggests that Niger State uses moulds more frequently than

Benue State. Furthermore, 74.0% and 74.0% of respondents in Benue State, respectively, utilized ploughing and harrowing techniques to prepare their land, in contrast to 57.8% and 53.5% in Niger. This demonstrated that Benue State made greater use of the ploughing and harrowing methods of land preparation. This could be explained by the yam growers in Benue State having access to additional equipment for harrowing and ploughing. In Benue and Niger States, respectively, 49.3% and 47.5% of respondents used ridge as the least common way of land preparation.

Table 4: Distribution of respondents based on the improved yam production technologies utilized

Variables	Benue State (n=200)	Niger State (n=199)
Utilization of improved yam production method	Freq (%)	Freq (%)
Yes	158 (79.0)	185 (93.0)
No	42 (21.0)	14 (7.0)
Land clearing method *		
Ploughing	117 (74.0)	104 (57.8)
Harrowing	117 (74.0)	99 (53.5)
Moulds	92 (58.2)	167 (90.2)
Ridges	78(49.3)	88 (47.5)
Holes	86 (54.4)	124 (67.0)
Improved Planting method *		
Yam mini-sett	74 (46.8)	151 (81.6)
Vine cutting	74 (46.8)	87 (47.0)
Whole-tuber	107 (67.7)	164 (88.6)
Mulching practices utilized*		
Dry vegetables	121 (76.5)	166 (89.7)
Compost materials	121 (76.5)	114 (61.6)
Crop residues	121 (76.5)	132 (71.3)
Fertilizer application method*		
Inorganic	117 (74.0)	142 (76.7)
Organic	112 (70.8)	144 (77.8)
Staking method*		
Tripod/Pyramid stake	110 (69.6)	110 (59.4)
Single pole stake	110 (69.6)	122 (65.9)
Cross pole stake	110 (69.6)	104 (56.2)
Weed control method*		
Manual	126 (79.7)	169 (91.3)
Mechanical	126 (79.7)	166 (89.7)
Harvesting method*		
Milking	118 (74.6)	97 (52.4)
Whole tube	118 (74.6)	164 (90.2)

Sources: Field Survey, 2019

Table 4 shows that yam mini-sett was used by 81.6% of the respondents in Niger State. This suggests that the majority of respondents in the research area planted yams using the mini-sett approach. This may be because subsistence farmers find yam mini setts to be more affordable and manageable. This result was in line with Okoro's (2008) findings that subsistence farmers can get higher yields by using yam mini-setts. Additionally, whole-tuber was used by 88.6% and 67.7% of responders in the states of Niger and Benue, respectively. This further demonstrates the high rate of whole tuber planting in Niger State. It is anticipated that planting complete tubers will result in higher yields. The Table shows that 89.7% of respondents in the state of Niger and 76.5% of respondents in the state of Benue, respectively, reported using dry vegetables as mulch. Furthermore, compost materials were used as mulching by 76.5% and 61.6% of respondents in Benue and Niger States, respectively. Additional research revealed that 76.5% and 71.3% of respondents in the states of Benue and Niger, respectively, reported using crop leftovers as mulching.

According to Table 4, the percentage of respondents in Niger and Benue States who used organic fertilizer (farm-yard manure) was 77.8% and 70.8%, respectively. Furthermore, 76.7% and 74.0% of respondents in Niger and Benue, respectively, reported using inorganic fertilizers (NPK). The table also shows that 69.6% of respondents in Benue State used cross-pole, single-pole, and tripod/pyramid stakes, respectively. In Niger State, however, 65.9%, 59.4%, and 56.2% of the respondents used cross poles, tripods/pyramids, and single pole stakes. This result demonstrated that respondents from all states in the study area used all staking practices. In addition, manual weeding was used by 91.3% and 79.7% of respondents in the states of Niger and Benue,

respectively. Family labour availability may be the cause of this. This may also be related to yam producers' conviction that hand-weeding produces superior results. But in Niger and Benue States, respectively, 89.7% and 79.7% of respondents used mechanical marriages. Herbicide application is a productive way to manage weeds while producing yams. This is because using herbicides is less expensive than pulling weeds by hand and offers effective weed control during the crucial yam growth stages.

According to the table, entire tuber harvesting was used by 90.2% and 74.6% of the respondents in the states of Niger and Benue, respectively. Utilizing the entire tuber improves maturity at an advanced stage. Furthermore, milking harvesting was used by 74.6% and 52.4% of respondents in the states of Benue and Niger, respectively. In terms of regenerating fresh yams that would be planted, farmers might benefit from the use of milking harvesting.

Effects of improved yam production technologies on yam output

Table 5 presents the findings of a multiple regression study on the effects of enhanced yam production technology on yam yield. The Coub-Douglas function was picked as the lead equation for Benue, while the linear function was chosen for the Niger States, based on the magnitude of the coefficient of multiple determination (R^2), the size and signs of the parameter estimates, as well as their statistical significance. The explanatory variables were well fitted into the model, as indicated by the F-statistics, which were all significant at the 1% probability level.

Table 5. Regression estimate on effects of improved yam production technologies on yam output of the respondents

Variables	Benue State (n=200)		Niger State (n=199)	
	Coub-Douglas		Linear	
Mulching	-0.0053	-0.11	4371.478	6.97***
Improved planting	0.8531	2.88***	45.57775	0.19
Herbicide	1.3466	26.31***	4159.544	2.19***
Fertilizer	0.1259	3.18***	47.23064	2.07**
Staking	-0.2381	-2.89***	-8.81384	-0.11
Weeding	-0.0168	0.41	803.8226	1.51
Land preparation	-0.7318	-1.48	192.6698	1.83*
Harvesting	0.0875	0.99	20.18527	0.00
Constant	8.2235	24.36***	671367	4.23***
R-square	0.8640		0.3374	
Adj R-squared	0.8583		0.3095	
F-value	151.72		12.09	

Sources: Field survey 2019

*** significant at 1% level of probability, **=Significant at 5% level of probability, *=significant at 10% level of probability

At the 1% probability level, the mulching coefficient in Niger State (0.4371) was shown to be positive and significant, suggesting that respondents in the two states will produce more yams if they use mulch on their yam crops appropriately. This is consistent with Akinola et al. (2012), who found that yam emergence rates increased by a considerable 46% when mulched instead of unmulched. On the other hand, at the 1% probability level, the coefficient result on the application of the enhanced planting method (0.8531) in Benue State was positive and significant. The coefficient of herbicide use in Niger State is (4159.544), whereas the coefficient for Benue State is (1.3466). Both results are positive and statistically significant at the 1% probability level. This suggests that the use of herbicides by the respondents in all states is anticipated to increase the amount of yams produced.

Additionally, the results of the fertilizer application coefficients in Benue State

(0.1259) and Niger State (4159.544) were positive and significant at the 1% and 5% level of probability, respectively. This suggests that having access to appropriate and sufficient fertilizer application in the study area will increase the output of yam production. Thus, it should come as no surprise that fertilizer had a significant effect on yam yield. At the 1% probability level, Benue State's coefficient of staking (-0.2381) was shown to be adversely significant. This suggests that Benue State's yam yield may drop as staking is used more frequently, maybe as a result of planting kinds that are not supported by staking. The results are consistent with Onwueme's (1978) findings, which stated that staking was a crucial process in the production of yams since staked plants produce a significantly larger yield than unstaked ones. At the 10% probability level, Niger State's coefficient of land preparation (192.67) was positively significant. This shows that the growers in the study area should expect their output to rise

with proper harrowing, ploughing, and ridging of land for yam production.

Conclusion

The results indicate that the majority of the yam growers in the research region were married men in their middle years with formal education. Additional research reveals that most respondents were aware of and used improved yam farming practices in addition to improved yam technologies. While most respondents used single pole stake staking, the majority also used mould under soil clearance, whole-tuber under planting techniques, dry

vegetables under mulching, and inorganic fertilizer. The productivity of yam growers was impacted by the coefficient of mulching, site preparation, improved planting technique, herbicide, fertilizer application, and staking. Therefore, to support women farmers in the research region, it is advised that extension agents be gender sensitive while disseminating information on enhanced yam production. The many organizations tasked with creating better yam production technology ought to make them accessible and reasonably priced for increased use.

REFERENCES

- Aniedu, O. C. (2016). Socio-economic determinants of the adoption of improved yam production technologies in Imo state, Nigeria. *Journal of agriculture and social research* 16(2):25–31.
- Ajieh, P. C (2012). Adoption of yam (*Dioscorea* spp.) miniset technology in Delta State, Nigeria, *Agricultura Tropica Et Subtropica* 45(2) :84-88
- Akinola, A. A. and Sofoluwe, N.A. (2012), Impact of mulching technology adoption on output and net return to yam farmers in Osun State, Nigeria, *Agrekon* 51(2):72-92.
- Benue State Geographic Information System (NIGIS) (2018) www.nigergis.com . Retrived on 30th October , 2018.
- Food and Agricultural Organization (2010). FAOSTATDATA.FAO, Rome, Italy. www.fao.org. accessed 23rd August, 2018
- Muhammad, S. (2015). Agricultural Extension: Strategies and Skills. Unitech Communication, *Journal of Animal and Plant Science* 26 (3), 245 – 253.
- National Population Commission (NPC) (2006), Provisional Census Figure of Nigeria: NPC/FGN, Abuja, Nigeria
- Niger State Geographic Information System (NIGIS) (2018) www.nigergis.com . Retrived on 30th October , 2018.
- Nahanga, V. and Becvarova, V. (2014). Yam Production as a Pillar of Food Security in Logo Local Government Area of Benue State, Nigeria. *European scientific Journal* 10(31), 27– 42.
- Ogaraku, A. O. and Usman, H.O. (2008). Storage rot of some yams (*Dioscorea*spp.) in Keffi and Nasarawa State Nigeria. *Production and Agricultural Technology* 4: 22-27.
- Okigbo, R.N. and Ogbonnaya, U.O. (2006). Antifungal effects of two tropical plant extracts (*Ocimumgratissimum*and *Aframomummelegueta*) on post- harvest yam rot. *African Journal of Biotechnology* 5(9):727 – 731.
- Okoro, J. K (2008). Awareness and Use of the Rapid Seed Yam Multiplication Technology by Farmers in Nigeria’s Yam Belt. *Production Agricultural Technology* 5 (1), 22-29.
- Omotesho, O. A. Falola, A. Muhammad-Lawal, A. and Oyeyemi A. (2012). Comparative Analysis of the Performances of Adopters and Non-Adopters of Yam
- Usongo, S., P. Idisi, O. Innocent, M. and Daniel, P. O (2014). An Assessment of yam production in Ukum Local Government Area of Benue State, Nigeria. In: *Proceedings of the 48th Annual Conference of the Agricultural Society of Nigeria*. Pp 281 -284.
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